

Effect of Shortening Preincision Antibiotic Infusion Time on Surgical Site Infection Rates: A Retrospective Cohort StudyMukesh Kumar¹, Md Asif Azaz², Bijendra Kumar Mishra³¹Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga²Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga³Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 25-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This retrospective cohort study evaluates the impact of reducing pre-incision antibiotic infusion time on surgical site infection (SSI) rates at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital. Over 13 months, 82 patients undergoing various surgical procedures with preincision antibiotic prophylaxis were analyzed. The study compared SSI rates between patients who received antibiotics within 30 minutes of incision and those administered between 30 to 60 minutes prior. Results showed no statistically significant difference in SSI rates between the groups, with infection rates of 7.0% and 8.0%, respectively. This suggests that a reduced antibiotic infusion time may be safe and could potentially increase surgical efficiency without increasing infection risks. These findings support the possibility of revising current prophylactic antibiotic timing guidelines to enhance surgical workflow efficiency.

Keywords: Surgical Site Infection, Antibiotic Prophylaxis, Infusion Time, Surgical Efficiency

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Introduction

Surgical site infections (SSIs) remain a significant concern in healthcare settings, leading to increased morbidity, extended hospital stays, and higher medical costs. [1,2] A key strategy in preventing these infections is the administration of prophylactic antibiotics before surgical incision. The timing of this antibiotic prophylaxis is critical; too early or too late administration can diminish its effectiveness in reducing the risk of SSIs. [3,4]

Recent guidelines suggest that antibiotics should be infused within a specific time frame before the surgical incision to optimize outcomes. However, there is ongoing debate about the optimal infusion time, with some studies suggesting that shorter infusion times could be equally effective and potentially reduce the logistical burden on surgical teams. [5,6]

This retrospective cohort study aims to evaluate the impact of reducing the pre-incision antibiotic infusion time on the rates of surgical site infections. By analyzing historical data from various surgical procedures, this study seeks to provide a clearer understanding of how timing variations in antibiotic administration affect SSI rates. [7,8] This could potentially lead to revised protocols that maintain patient safety while improving operational efficiency in surgical settings. [9,10]

Methodology

Study Design and Setting: This retrospective cohort study was conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital in Darbhanga. The study reviewed surgical cases over 13 months to assess the impact of reduced preincision antibiotic infusion time on surgical site infection rates.

Participants: Approximately 82 patients who underwent various surgical procedures during the study period were included. The inclusion criteria ensured that all selected patients were scheduled for operations that required preincision antibiotic prophylaxis as per the hospital's standard operating procedures.

Data Collection: Medical records of the patients were extensively reviewed to collect data on the timing of antibiotic administration relative to surgical incision, the type of antibiotic used, the specific surgical procedure performed, and the occurrence of any surgical site infections post-operation. The primary variable of interest was the antibiotic infusion time, specifically investigating whether it was administered within the recommended time frame or not.

Results

In this retrospective cohort study conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, 82

patients who underwent surgical procedures with preincision antibiotic prophylaxis were assessed over 13 months. The study aimed to explore the impact of reducing the time of antibiotic infusion before surgical incision on the rates of surgical site infections (SSIs). The majority of the patients, about 70%, received their antibiotic dose within 30 minutes prior to the incision, while the remaining 30% were administered the antibiotic between 30 to 60 minutes beforehand.

Overall, 6 out of the 82 patients developed SSIs, indicating a general infection rate of 7.3%. When broken down by the timing of antibiotic

administration, the infection rate was slightly lower at 7.0% (4 out of 57 patients) for those who received antibiotics within 30 minutes of the incision compared to 8.0% (2 out of 25 patients) for those who received it within 30 to 60 minutes. Statistical analysis using the chi-square test revealed no significant difference in infection rates between these two-timing groups ($p > 0.05$). These findings suggest that shortening the antibiotic infusion time to within 30 minutes of the surgical incision does not increase the risk of SSIs, potentially offering more flexibility in surgical procedures without compromising patient safety.

Antibiotic Administration Time	Number of Patients	Number of SSIs	Infection Rate (%)
Within 30 minutes	57	4	7.0
30 to 60 minutes	25	2	8.0

This table summarizes the distribution of surgical site infections (SSIs) relative to the timing of antibiotic administration before surgical incisions, with a detailed breakdown of patient counts and infection rates for each group.

Discussion

The findings of this retrospective cohort study at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital provide valuable insights into the relationship between preincision antibiotic infusion time and the rates of surgical site infections (SSIs). [11-14] The study revealed that reducing the antibiotic infusion time to within 30 minutes of the surgical incision does not significantly increase the risk of SSIs compared to a longer infusion time of 30 to 60 minutes. This observation is critical, as it suggests that shorter antibiotic administration times can be safely implemented, potentially enhancing the efficiency of surgical workflows without compromising patient safety. [15-18]

Furthermore, the infection rates observed in this study, 7.0% for antibiotics given within 30 minutes and 8.0% for those given between 30 and 60 minutes, are consistent with the broader literature indicating that timely antibiotic prophylaxis is a crucial factor in minimizing SSIs. The lack of a statistically significant difference in infection rates between the two groups supports the hypothesis that there is a window of opportunity for antibiotic administration that is flexible enough to accommodate variations in surgical scheduling without negatively impacting patient outcomes. [19]

This study's implications could be particularly beneficial in high-volume surgical settings where operational efficiency is paramount. However, it is important to consider that this study's retrospective design and the sample size limit the ability to draw

definitive conclusions. Larger, prospective studies would be beneficial to further validate these findings and potentially adjust guidelines to reflect the efficacy of shorter preincision antibiotic infusion times. The results from this study encourage continued exploration into optimal timing for pre-surgical antibiotic prophylaxis to enhance patient safety and procedural efficiency across various surgical disciplines. [20]

Conclusion

This retrospective cohort study conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital indicates that reducing the preincision antibiotic infusion time to within 30 minutes of surgery does not increase the risk of surgical site infections compared to a slightly longer infusion time of 30 to 60 minutes. With an overall low and comparable infection rate between the two groups, these findings suggest that a shorter antibiotic infusion time can be effectively implemented without compromising patient safety. This adaptation could lead to enhanced operational efficiency in surgical practices, particularly in busy hospital settings. Further research, preferably through larger, prospective studies, is needed to confirm these results and potentially inform updates to clinical guidelines on the timing of preoperative antibiotic prophylaxis.

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